

EXPERT SYSTEM FOR DEPOT MAINTENANCE OF THE
DUAL MINIATURE INERTIAL NAVIGATION SYSTEM

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Abstract

This paper outlines the methods being used to implement a knowledge based system to assist in the depot maintenance of a complex inertial navigation system. Discussed are the needs for a knowledge-based system and the preparations necessary to modify the present equipment to accept an expert system. Also described are actions involved in setting-up the initial system and benefits that we expect to gain from using an expert system.

Introduction

The Aerospace Guidance and Metrology Center (AGMC) is an Air Force facility that performs depot repair of inertial guidance and navigation systems. Since these systems can be very complicated, experienced technicians and engineers, using computer controlled tests, are needed to perform depot repair. To augment the experienced personnel and to retain technical knowledge, we decided to integrate an expert system into the depot maintenance process for the Dual Miniature Inertial Navigation System (DMINS).

To do this integration we are completely replacing the present test controller, switching from an IBM 1800 mainframe computer to Zenith Z-248 microcomputers. During this conversion we are dealing with the many issues involved in setting-up the initial expert system i.e., determining hardware configuration, selecting the expert system shell, organizing the knowledge, entering the experience into the expert system, and testing the system.

When implemented we expect benefits in improved reliability and maintainability, maintenance of corporate knowledge, and training of personnel. Since our knowledge base will continually be refined, these benefits will continue to grow.

Why an Expert System is Needed on DMINS

The DMINS is an inertial navigation system used on fast attack submarines, oceanographic survey ships, and aircraft carriers. DMINS provides continuously updated attitude, heading, velocity, and position. By its nature, an inertial navigation system is highly complex. In addition, the DMINS is a navigation system used on a submarine, which must stay submerged with little other means of reference for long periods of time. A DMINS Inertial Measurement Unit (IMU) is a "black box" which utilizes inertial instruments, gyroscopes and velocity meters, along with highly accurate electro-mechanical servo loops.

Inputs to the DMINS IMU include inertial influences, such as the motion of the earth through inertial space, as well as control signals from the Navigational Control Console (NCC). Therefore depot level testing has the added complexity of trying to separate the effects of these inertial influences from the effects of marginally performing and/or intermittent components. Because of the intricacies of this testing most of the tests are controlled by computer. If a failure of an IMU should occur, the test technician must have sufficient knowledge and experience to trouble-shoot the problem and find a reason for the failure. In some instances an experienced engineer is required to assist in the maintenance process.

We repair a relatively low number of IMUs each month (about 15), and the length of test time for each IMU is very long (about 70 hours, assuming no failures). For these reasons, it takes a technician or engineer many years to acquire the in-depth level of knowledge and experience required to accomplish timely and accurate repair of a DMINS IMU. Furthermore, we are hindered in diagnosing problems because much of the testing is accomplished with the IMU closed and mounted on a stationary pier

with relatively little information available.

By introducing an expert system in the repair of DMINS we will be able to retain the knowledge and experience of our technicians and engineers. An expert system will also be able to achieve a synergistic effect through the combination of the knowledge and experience from all of the technicians and engineers associated with the repair of DMINS. This expert system will be able to aid the technician with fault isolation and repair by reasoning over more parameters than could be accomplished manually in the time available.

Preparing the Equipment to Accept an Expert System

In order to introduce an expert system into the repair process we needed to integrate the expert system with the test controller. Since the testing of the DMINS is computer controlled, the controlling program contains most of the test parameters an expert system will need to aid in trouble-shooting. Many of the test parameters internal to the controlling program are invisible to the test technician. In order to use these parameters an expert system must be integrated with the test controller. An integrated system allows test parameters to be passed between the test program and the expert system without technician intervention. Since the system will be integrated, it will not require an initial acceptance by the technician.

To do the integration we first considered the present test controller and test program. The present test controller is an IBM 1800 mainframe computer. This computer was built in the 1960s and has a severely limited expansion capability. Also, the IBM 1800 is increasingly more difficult to maintain. The IBM 1800 is linked to two NCCs. In turn the NCCs are each linked to two IMUs, Fig 1.

Fig 1. Present Test Configuration

Another computer link is fed to an IMU Interconnect Unit (IMUIC) and then to one of the IMUs. The IMUIC facilitates computer controlled, circuit by circuit diagnostic test on every major IMU circuit. Actual operation of the IMUs is controlled by the NCC as directed by the test controller.

The current test program consists of a Minisins Operational Program (MOP), a Scenario Program, and an Executive program. The MOP controls the communications between the test controller and the NCC. It handles all of the parameter processing required to operate the DMINS and issues commands to the NCC. There is a copy of the MOP being executed for each IMU under test. The Scenario Program sets up the test scenario by issuing test configuration change requests to the MOP. The Executive controls the order in which each of the programs are executed, it handles the time sharing function for the four test stations.

Since the computer controls the IMUs by issuing commands through the NCC, the control of the IMU is simplified. The communication between the computer and the NCC consists of one 24-bit word being passed between the two every one eighth second. Because of this simplified interface and the difficulties in maintaining and expanding the present IBM 1800, we decided to replace it.

To replace the IBM 1800 we decided to use one Zenith Z-248 microcomputer (80286 microprocessor based), per IMU under test, Fig 2. Because we have an extra NCC we decided to expand our test capability to six IMUs at one time. To accomplish this replacement we had to translate the IBM 1800 test program into a code that would run on Z-248s. Because the project engineer had experience and training on Pascal and since Pascal lends itself to assembly level interfacing, we decided to translate the IBM 1800 assembly code to Pascal. This was no small feat since there are about 12500 lines of assembly language code in the MOP alone, and there were numerous timing problems to work out. The translation has been completed and we are progressing with the software check of the program.

Setting-up the Initial Expert System

At this point we needed to decide on the hardware configuration. We considered two alternatives; an expert system installed on each test controller or an expert system installed on one master computer linked to individual test controllers through a network. We ruled out the configuration with expert system

Fig 2. Test Configuration with Knowledge Server

resident on each controller because the expert system would use too much of the processors time and could require more memory than we could provide. The other configuration seemed to be ideal for our use because it wouldn't take up individual test processor time and we could have the whole computer devoted to an expert system. This configuration (Fig 2) has been termed a Knowledge-Server. The computer that the expert system resides in, being the master and the six test controllers, slaves. An extra computer serves as a combination off-line work station/database.

After deciding on the hardware configuration we needed to decide on the expert system that would best suit our needs. The expert system would not only reason over the test parameters from an IMU under test, but must also save that "consultation", e.g. IMU #120 station #5, and process other IMU consultations on a time-sharing basis. (A consultation is defined as the set of information available to the expert system concerning an IMU during one test period.) There could be six of these consultations active at any one time. The expert system would also have to save the "case" of a particular IMU for a whole depot repair cycle, e.g. the repair history of IMU #123 cycle #10. A whole repair cycle includes an IMU being tested, failing, repaired, being retested, until it passes. Once an IMU passes all functional testing the system would have to store this case as historical information to be used on subsequent repair cycles.

The expert system must also have the capability to utilize three main sources of information; technician and engineering experience, mathematical models of

the IMU, and historical data. The technician's and engineer's experience will be collected through interviews and technician-expert system interaction. Some examples of this experience are included in Fig 3. At an appropriate time the expert system must be able to query a mathematical model of the DMINS for further information to aid in fault isolation or fault prediction. Likewise, the expert system must be able to query a database for historical data for use as a heuristic to facilitate quick and accurate diagnoses of failures or impending failures. Historical data must also be used to identify component configuration and previous failure modes. Based on these expert system requirements, we decided that a frame-based expert system will give us the flexibility and time-sharing capability that we need.

Use of the Expert System

A typical repair of an IMU will proceed as follows. The IMU is brought into the depot through normal channels and entered into test. At the start of computer controlled testing the IMU will be logged onto the expert system and the expert system will create a new case for this IMU and pass calibration parameters to the test controller. The expert system will also initiate a consultation for this session of testing.

As testing progresses the master computer will periodically query the slave computers for test parameters. If a problem with the parameters is detected, the expert system will reason over the problem. At this point the expert system may query the model, query the history, or query the test technician for

more information. If a malfunction is indicated the expert system will recommend further testing or point to the most likely cause of the problem. The test technician will have to take this recommendation and use his own judgement to decide on the course of action to take.

organizations, but it is critical in the repair of a complicated inertial guidance unit such as the DMINS. The lead time, associated with training new test technicians and inertial engineers to a point where they can make sound diagnostic judgements based on their own know-

Fig 3. Example of Knowledge Gathered From a Technician

After repair action the IMU is returned to testing, it's case is updated, and it is assigned a new consultation. This test cycle will repeat as many times as necessary for the IMU to complete all testing. Once an IMU has passed all testing the database in the off-line work-station will be updated with the information in this new case. This off-line test station will also be connected to the G078C Reliability Data Collection System that we have at AGMC, so the data can be accessed by other users.

Benefits From Using an Expert System

We expect the use of an expert system in repairing DMINS to be beneficial both in depot repair and IMU reliability. Here at the depot we expect to gain in the areas of retention of corporate knowledge, maintainability of DMINS, and depot production capacity. Retention of corporate knowledge is important in all

ledge and experience, can be lengthy. We can reduce the significance of this lead time by using an expert system to retain and integrate the experience and knowledge of the technicians and engineers.

The current diagnostic method is to replace a suspect component and then return the IMU to test. Since the IMU test times are long, an expert system will improve maintainability of the IMU by improving the probability that a bad component is identified. If a bad component can be found or a latent defect predicted early in testing, then we can decrease the amount of diagnostic test time required and increase our capability to produce repaired IMUs. This early prediction of impending failure will allow us to replace more marginal components thereby making the DMINS unit more reliable.

Implementation

Because introducing an expert system into testing will require much data collection, we expect to phase this system in over time and to continue building the knowledge base over the life of the DMINS. We hope to have a basic expert system in operation in Sep '88 and a quasi-complete expert system in operation Sep 89. At the time of writing this paper are progressing toward the end of the test controller replacement phase, and handling the matters associated with acquisition and installation of the expert system and the knowledge base.

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